

**The Implementation of Total Physical Response (TPR) in
Teaching Speaking**

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***Abstract:** Generally, speaking skill is one of the essential skills that must be acquired by students at school. The students are hoped to be able to communicate in English in their daily activities. Event though, student unrarely use it because feeling unconfident and absolutely need a way to solve the problem. This research would investigate the implementation of TPR in Teaching Speaking. To analyze how TPR is used by teacher and students' response in learning English especially speaking skill, qualitativite methodologies ar employed. Teacher and English learners from SMPN 1 Purwosari in the 8th grade served as the participants. Observation, questionnaires, and interviews were used to collect the data. The most students gave positive response toward the implemetation of TPR in learning speaking. It was proved from the result of the interview and questionnare. The students had fun to learn English in speaking by using many movements during learning activity and they were able to follow their teacher's intruction well. However, few students did not interest toward TPR in learning English speaking lessoon. The suggestion for other researchers is to investigate the implementation TPR in teaching other languages aspect such as grammar. The researchers are also suggested to investigate the effectiveness of TPR teaching method to improve students' particular English skill.*

Key words: TPR, Speaking skill, Teaching speaking

INTRODUCTION

Speaking skill is one of the essential skills that must be acquired by students at school. The students are hoped to be able to communicate in English in their daily activities. However, the students sometimes find difficulties in speaking which is probably caused by their confident. They also have lack of

English vocabularies and some students also seldom practice their speaking skill at school.

Another factor caused students face obstacles to master speaking is many English teachers who focuses more on delivering the grammatical terms instead of guiding the students to use the language, especially in speaking. The curricullum actually has already been designed to focus more in productive skills of the language. In fact, most of teachers still implement the traditional way in teaching English such as giving them understanding more about grammar. This situation makes the students lack of practice, and it results on the improvement of the students ability in speaking.

The last problem of students in master speaking is caused by the teaching method chosen by the teacher. (Tasmia, 2019) observed that many people got difficulties to learn English especially in speaking because of the lack of teaching time and ineffective teaching method. Students need a teacher who is able to use proper teaching method in teaching speaking. The method implemented by the teacher must be able to invite the students to speak actively in the classroom. During the learning process, to solve their problem, it is a role of the teacher to provide some methods effectively in teaching speaking. A teacher has a role to provide effective teaching method to solve students' problem in the classroom (Penny Ur's, 2009).

Total Physical Response (TPR) is one of the teaching methods which can be used to help the students to master speaking skill. According to (Astutik

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et al, 2019), she stated that the basic background of TPR is that the students are able to understand and perform teacher's instructions. (Samir, 2017) said that TPR is the method which is able to make students be brave and be interested in speaking activity. This method is considered suitable to be implemented in teaching speaking since it will help and encourage students to increase their motivation in learning English. Besides, this method is also able to make the students enjoy to study since the activity is full of body movement. Most students are excited when the teacher invites them to do physical activity rather than sitting nicely on their seat (Rachmawati & Rahayu, 2020).

LITERATURE REVIEW

The Nature of Total Physical Response

Total Physical Response is teaching-learning strategy developed by Dr. James Asher, a professor of psychology at San Joe State University. Before the students recognize the new language like speaking, writing, or reading, they learn TPR first in language. TPR was developed in order to reduce the stress that people feel when studying foreign languages and thereby encourage students to persist in their study beyond a beginning level of proficiency (Larsen and Freeman, 2011).

Teaching Speaking Using Total Physical Response

Naturally, TPR method is used in teaching vocabulary. Yet, in some cases, this method is also used by some teachers for teaching speaking. Frequently, they use this method in teaching speaking material in which requires the students do some body movement. In this research, the researcher is going to investigate the use of TPR in teaching giving instruction and prohibition material in class eight. The followings are the steps of the implementation of TPR in teaching speaking:

1. The teacher starts implement TPR when he introduces instruction expression in English using gesture such as clean the blackboard, water the plant, close the door, play a guitar, drink a coffee, etc.
2. The teacher says and performs the expression, then the students imitate the action
3. The teacher only says the expression, and the students perform the action together
4. The teacher explains the way to make instruction and prohibition expression).

METHODOLOGY

The researcher decides to apply a descriptive qualitative research. This research aims to portray the phenomenon through interview, observing and documenting (Ary et al. 2010). The researcher described all the activities while conducting the research. The researcher wanted to know how to implement TPR in teaching speaking. Moreover, the researcher used a descriptive qualitative approach to explore, analyse and describe all of them clearly. The subjects of the study were English teacher and students in the ninth grade at SMPN 1 Purwosari. The researcher chose that school, since one of the English teachers there frequently used TPR in teaching English, especially speaking skill. Observation, questionnaires, and interviews were used to collect the data. The researcher analyzed the data collected by using (Miles and Huberman, 1994) data analysis model. There are some activities in this analysis technique; they are, condensation (definisi), data display, and conclusion drawing/verification. After collecting the data, the researcher will do data reduction by making a main summary, choosing the main points, and deleting useless ones.

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FINDING AND DISCUSSION

According to the data about the implementation of TPR in teaching speaking, we could take some discussions. The first was about whether the teacher had implemented TPR based on proper steps or syntaxes. The data of observation showed that the teacher implemented TPR based on the proper steps. In teaching speaking instruction and prohibition topic, the teacher did not only introduce the expression orally, but he also used gesture to explain the meaning of each expression. The teacher also asked the students to perform together with him. To make sure that the students understand the expression, the teacher said the expression, and the students performed the expression. The teacher also asked the students to perform the expression either in individual or in a group. What the teacher did in speaking class above is suitable to the principles of TPR found by (Asher, 2007), they are the teacher gave and performed command, the teacher and the students performed the command together, only the students performed the command given by the teacher, the student performed the command individually, and the students performed the command in a group.

From observation, we could also see that the teacher was very excited and expressive in using his gesture to explain the meaning of expression. The teacher also used expressive intonation in telling every single expression of prohibition and intonation. From the observation, we could also see that teacher also invited the students to imitate the expression orally. The teacher also asked the students to demonstrate the expression presented by the teacher. The teacher also asked the students to express and demonstrate as excited as possible. The teacher also did not implement TPR too fast in order make the students follow every instruction easily. TPR should not be implemented too fast (Larsen and freeman, 2011). It is recommended that a teacher present three commands at a time. After students feel successful with these, three more can be taught.

To make the class more interesting, the teacher invited the students to play “gesture game”. The teacher asked the students to make a group, show the gesture of particular expression, and ask other groups to guess what expression it is. The role of the teacher in this activity was as facilitator of the students in playing the game. The students did not look feeling stress in speaking class using TPT. Most of them were happy in speaking class. TPR was developed in order to reduce the stress people feel when studying foreign languages and thereby encourage students to persist in their study beyond a beginning level of proficiency, (Larsen and Freeman, 2011).

In observation, we could also see how the students’ feeling during learning speaking using TPR. Most students were very excited to engage speaking activity using TPR. The students looked attracted to do kinesthetic activity by imitating the instruction and prohibition expression introduced by the teacher. Physical movement is appropriate with the characteristics of young learners, because they like to be involved in kinaesthetic activities (Larsen and Freeman, 2011). Most students were also very expressive to say the expression and show an attractive gesture for each expression. The students looked more excited when the teacher invited them to play “gesture game”. Most of them were very enthusiastic to show the gesture that should be guessed by other groups. They were also very excited to guess the gesture shown by other groups. In other words, from discussion, TPR successfully created fun classroom atmosphere. This method was able to encourage students’ interest and excitement to learn speaking.

According to the finding from the data of questionnaire, we could take some discussions. Based on the data of questionnaire about students feeling taught by expressive teacher, most students said that they were very happy having speaking class with expressive teacher. The data from the interview also showed that one of the students interviewed said that when he was taught by expressive teacher he felt very happy and did not feel sleepy during speaking class. The data from the questionnaire also presented that most students were happy to be taught by the teacher who usually implemented fun teaching

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method. From the finding of data questionnaire, we could also have a discussion about students' feeling or response when learning speaking using TPR teaching method. According to students' answer, most of students said that TPR was able to make them to become more active during speaking class. The data from interview also showed that one of the reason why the student liked TPR was caused by the method was not bored and made them active in the classroom. TPR was also able to encourage students' excitement in speaking class. This statement was proven by the finding from the questionnaire; it was many students could enjoy speaking class using TPR method. The data from the interview also showed that the student felt pleasure and happy to learn speaking using TPR because they did many fun gestures and expression during speaking class. They did not just sit on the chairs, but the teacher also asked them to do many movements in showing the expression discussed. Dealing with whether TPR was able to improve students' speaking ability, only some students said that this method successfully helped them to improve speaking. In other words, this method was successfully able to make most students feel happy in speaking class, but it had not successfully to improve all students' speaking ability.

CONCLUSION

The Total Physical Response (TPR) teaching method has been implemented properly by the teacher in teaching speaking. The teacher had implemented the steps or syntaxes of TPR, they were telling the meaning of instruction and prohibition expression using gesture, asking the student to imitate the gesture, and inviting the students to show the gesture in explaining the expression given by the teacher. The implementation of TPR has successfully encouraged students' interest in speaking class. During speaking class, it is found that most students were very active and excited in speaking activity. Most students responded and agreed that TPR was one of fun teaching method in speaking class. The implementation of TPR in speaking class had helped them to learn speaking with fun atmosphere. Most students were very excited in speaking class using TPR. They are interested to this method since this method invited the students to do motoric activity. Most students also said that this method helped them to be more active in speaking class. This method successfully invited the students to keep active saying the expression and showing the gesture of each expression.

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